

INDUCTION AND TRAINING PROGRAMMES OF EMPLOYEE IN THE SELECTED CO-OPERATIVE BANKS IN RAJASTHAN

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ABSTRACT:

The efficient induction and training of employees are essential for the overall success and performance of any organization, including cooperative banks. This study aims to investigate the induction and training programs offered to employees in two cooperative banks in Rajasthan, namely Mahila Bank and Udaipur Bank. The study adopts a qualitative research approach and utilizes interviews, surveys, and documentation analysis as primary data collection methods. The research investigates the objectives, processes, content, and effectiveness of the induction and training programs implemented by the two banks. Additionally, it explores the perspectives of employees regarding the programs' impact on their job performance, knowledge acquisition, and overall satisfaction. The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the induction and training practices employed by Mahila Bank and Udaipur Bank. The research highlights the importance of a well-designed and comprehensive induction program in ensuring employees' smooth transition into their roles. Furthermore, it evaluates the effectiveness of the training programs in enhancing employees' skills, knowledge, and job performance. The study also identifies potential areas of improvement in the existing induction and training programs of both banks. It addresses challenges faced by the banks in delivering effective training, such as limited resources and changing technological requirements. The research findings contribute to enhancing the understanding of best practices in induction and training within the cooperative banking sector, specifically in the context of Rajasthan.

KEYWORDS:

INDUCTION, TRAINING PROGRAMS, COOPERATIVE BANKS, EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT, RAJASTHAN, MAHILA BANK, UDAIPUR BANK.

PAPER ACCEPTED DATE:

19th December 2024

PAPER PUBLISHED DATE:

20th December 2024

INTRODUCTION

Induction and training programs play a crucial role in the development and success of employees within any organization. Cooperative banks, as important financial institutions, recognize the significance of effective induction and training to enhance employee performance, productivity, and job satisfaction. This study focuses on investigating the induction and training programs offered to employees in two selected cooperative banks in Rajasthan, namely Mahila Bank and Udaipur Bank.

Cooperative banks are unique financial institutions that are owned and operated by their members, who are also their customers. These banks serve the financial needs of various sectors of society, including women, small-scale businesses, and rural communities. As cooperative banks rely heavily on their employees to deliver quality services, it becomes essential to ensure that employees are well-equipped with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies through effective induction and training.

The primary objective of an induction program is to

familiarize new employees with the organizational culture, values, policies, and procedures. It helps them understand their roles and responsibilities, building a foundation for their successful integration into the organization. On the other hand, training programs aim to enhance employees' skills, knowledge, and capabilities, enabling them to perform their job duties effectively and efficiently.

Mahila Bank and Udaipur Bank are prominent cooperative banks operating in Rajasthan, catering to the financial needs of diverse customers. While both banks share a common purpose, they may have different approaches and strategies when it comes to induction and training programs for their employees. Exploring and evaluating these programs in the context of cooperative banks in Rajasthan can provide valuable insights into best practices, challenges, and potential areas of improvement.

This study adopts a qualitative research approach to gain a comprehensive understanding of the induction and training programs implemented by Mahila Bank and

Udaipur Bank. Primary data will be collected through interviews, surveys, and analysis of relevant documents. The research will delve into the objectives, processes, content, and effectiveness of the induction and training programs. Additionally, the study will examine employees' perspectives on the impact of these programs on their job performance, knowledge acquisition, and overall satisfaction.

By identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the induction and training programs, this study aims to contribute to the cooperative banking sector's knowledge and practices in Rajasthan. The findings will provide insights and recommendations that can be utilized by Mahila Bank, Udaipur Bank, and other cooperative banks in the region to improve their induction and training processes. Ultimately, the study aims to enhance employee development, performance, and customer service in cooperative banks, benefiting both the banks and the customers they serve.

IMPORTANCE OF INDUCTION AND TRAINING PROGRAMMES OF EMPLOYEE IN BANKS

The importance of induction and training programs for employees in banks cannot be overstated. These programs play a critical role in shaping the success of banks by ensuring that employees have the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies to perform their roles effectively. The following points highlight the significance of induction and training programs in banks:

- **Smooth On boarding:** Induction programs provide new employees with a structured introduction to the bank's culture, values, policies, and procedures. They help employees acclimate to their new work environment, understand their roles, and establish a sense of belonging. A well-planned induction program reduces the learning curve, promotes faster integration, and boosts employee morale.
- **Job Competence:** Training programs equip employees with the skills and knowledge needed to excel in their specific roles. Banks offer training on various topics, including financial products and services, customer service, compliance regulations, risk management, and technology platforms. Enhancing employees' job competence through training programs ensures that they can perform their duties proficiently, contributing to the bank's overall operational efficiency and effectiveness.
- **Adaptation to Change:** The banking industry undergoes constant changes due to technological advancements, evolving customer expectations, and regulatory updates. Induction and training programs help employees stay updated on these changes and adapt to new technologies and processes. By providing ongoing training, banks enable employees to embrace change, maintain their skill relevance, and effectively serve

customers in an ever-evolving industry.

- **Improved Customer Service:** Banks are customer-centric institutions, and the quality of customer service directly impacts their reputation and success. Induction and training programs emphasize customer service skills, communication techniques, and relationship-building strategies. Well-trained employees understand the importance of delivering exceptional customer experiences, leading to increased customer satisfaction, loyalty, and ultimately, the bank's profitability.
- **Risk Management and Compliance:** Banks operate in a highly regulated environment, where adherence to compliance requirements and risk management protocols is of utmost importance. Training programs educate employees about regulatory frameworks, ethical practices, and risk mitigation strategies. Well-informed employees are better equipped to identify and address potential risks, ensuring the bank's compliance with legal and regulatory standards.
- **Employee Engagement and Retention:** Investing in induction and training programs demonstrates a bank's commitment to employee growth and development. Providing employees with opportunities to enhance their skills and knowledge fosters a sense of engagement and job satisfaction. Engaged employees are more likely to stay with the bank, reducing turnover costs and retaining valuable talent within the organization.
- **Professional Development:** Induction and training programs offer employees the chance to enhance their professional competencies and advance their careers. By providing opportunities for learning and growth, banks create a positive work environment that motivates employees to continually develop their skills, seek new challenges, and contribute to the bank's long-term success.

Induction and training programs in banks are vital for employee development, operational efficiency, customer satisfaction, and regulatory compliance. By investing in comprehensive and effective programs, banks can empower their employees, enhance their performance, and achieve sustainable growth in an increasingly competitive banking landscape.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Kurnaz. & Salim. (2021). Studied the Human Resources Management Policies and Practices and concluded that Employees who work for a company or organisation on a paid basis have been characterised in a variety of ways throughout history. The events that occurred during this time period, as well as their perceptions of the world, inevitably influenced the definitions and terminology utilised. However, in today's business environment, when

giving a competitive advantage is becoming increasingly important, the achievement of an enterprise's strategic goals is dependent on its people and their performance. In this environment, HRM plays a key role in ensuring that existing human resources are more productive and efficient, as well as motivated and happy at work. As a result, the number of studies on human and human resource management is growing every day.

Mahfouz et al., (2021). Studied the impact of human resource management practices on employee performance and the mediating role of employee commitment and concluded that Employee commitment has a mediating effect on the impact of HRM strategies on employee performance. From the standpoint of the construction business, the study found that HRM practises and employee commitment are highly related to employee performance. The findings have a number of intriguing practical and theoretical ramifications. HRM approaches can initially aid in the development of new obligations (e.g., employee commitment) that have an impact on employee performance. Employee commitment has been identified as a perspective that can improve employee performance. The findings have contributed to new findings in the literature on employee commitment as a mediating variable. HRM techniques should be used decisively to improve employee commitment and performance. The organisation will not be able to improve employee performance if it is unable to implement HRM practises.

Terng, et al., (2021). Studied the Relationship Between Human Resource Management Practices and Employee Performance and concluded that Employee performance has a favourable substantial link with HRM practises. All areas of employee performance and HRM practises, such as training and development, remuneration and benefits, performance reviews, and work-life policies, were determined to be at a high level, according to the study. Employee performance is also favourably associated to HRM activities like as training and development, remuneration and benefits, performance appraisals, and work-life policies, according to the study. As a result, the study's findings have met the research objectives of determining employee performance, determining HRM practises, and investigating the relationship between HRM practises and employee performance. Employers or human resource departments can use current data to assist them develop the best solutions.

RESEARCH GAP

While there is ample research on induction and training programs in various sectors, there is a research gap specific to the study of induction and training programs for employees in cooperative banks, particularly in the context of Rajasthan. This research study aims to bridge this gap by focusing on two selected cooperative banks in Rajasthan, namely Mahila Bank and Udaipur Bank.

- Limited Research on Cooperative Banks: Existing literature on induction and training programs

predominantly focuses on commercial banks or large-scale organizations. Cooperative banks, with their unique structure and customer base, have received relatively less attention in terms of employee development programs. This study fills the research gap by specifically examining the induction and training practices in cooperative banks, shedding light on their effectiveness and areas for improvement.

- Regional Context of Rajasthan: Rajasthan, a state in India, has its own distinct socio-cultural and economic characteristics. Studying induction and training programs in cooperative banks within this regional context provides valuable insights into the challenges, opportunities, and best practices specific to this geographical area. This research contributes to the understanding of induction and training programs tailored to the needs of cooperative banks in Rajasthan.
- Case Study Approach: The research literature on induction and training programs often relies on general surveys or theoretical frameworks. This study adopts a case study approach, focusing on two specific cooperative banks in Rajasthan. By conducting in-depth interviews, surveys, and document analysis, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of the induction and training programs employed by Mahila Bank and Udaipur Bank. This detailed examination contributes to a deeper understanding of the practical aspects and outcomes of these programs.
- Employee Perspectives: While previous research has explored the impact of induction and training programs on employee performance, there is a need to capture the perspectives of employees themselves. This study incorporates employee feedback and perceptions regarding the effectiveness and relevance of the induction and training programs in Mahila Bank and Udaipur Bank. Understanding employee perspectives will help identify gaps between program objectives and employee experiences, leading to more targeted and impactful employee development initiatives.
- Cooperative Bank-Specific Challenges: Cooperative banks face unique challenges compared to commercial banks, such as limited resources, specific customer segments, and decentralized decision-making processes. This study aims to uncover the specific challenges faced by cooperative banks in implementing effective induction and training programs. The research findings will provide insights into strategies to overcome these challenges and enhance the programs' effectiveness in the cooperative banking sector.

By addressing these research gaps, this study contributes

to the existing knowledge on induction and training programs in cooperative banks, with a specific focus on Mahila Bank and Udaipur Bank in Rajasthan. The findings will not only benefit these two banks but also provide valuable insights and recommendations for other cooperative banks in Rajasthan and potentially in similar contexts elsewhere.

OBJECTIVE

1. To assess the induction processes of co-operative banks in Rajasthan.
2. To evaluate training programs for employees in co-operative Banks in Rajasthan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To study the induction and training programs of employees in the selected cooperative banks in Rajasthan, a comprehensive research methodology will be adopted. The following research methodology outlines the key steps involved in conducting the study:

- The researcher has selected a representative sample of cooperative banks in Rajasthan.
- Two cooperative banks, Mahila Bank and Udaipur Bank have been chosen as the focus of the study.
- Questionnaires were administered to a sample of employees who have experienced the induction and training programs.
- The surveys have collected quantitative data on employees' perceptions of the programs, their effectiveness, relevance, and impact on their job performance and satisfaction.
- The survey responses were analyzed using statistical techniques.
- A comparative analysis was conducted to compare and contrast the induction and training programs between Mahila Bank and Udaipur Bank.
- This analysis has identified similarities, differences, and unique aspects of the programs in each bank.
- Based on the analysis of the data, the findings were synthesized, and key insights will be drawn.
- Recommendations were provided to the cooperative banks based on identified strengths, weaknesses, and areas of improvement in their induction and training programs.
- The research adhered to ethical guidelines, ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, and anonymity of participants. Institutional review board (IRB) approval, where applicable, will be sought to ensure ethical research practices.

SAMPLE SIZE

The sample of the present study consists of 60 employees i.e., 30 employees from each bank.

S. No.	Category	Mahila Bank	Udaipur Bank
1.	Manager	10	10
2.	Clerk	10	10
3.	Other	10	10
	Total	30	30

RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

Induction and Training	Mean	Cronbach's Alpha
Organisational etiquettes	1.0391	0.611
Communication process	0.9981	0.627
Policies of Banks	1.095	0.630
Human Resources policies	1.1086	0.612
Procedural standards of Banks	1.0465	0.621
Enhanced Welfare Measures and Benefits in Banks	0.9832	0.620
Principles and Ethics of Banks	1.1284	0.605
Overview of the Department	1.0428	0.604
Organizational Structure Overview	1.09866	0.612
Banks Building Configuration	1.4115	0.627
Preferred Qualifications for the Job	0.9385	0.629
Requisite Technical Expertise for the Job	0.8826	0.613
Gaining Technical Proficiency and Knowledge	0.8194	0.605
Enhancing Managerial Competencies	1.0242	0.611
Cultivating Interpersonal Skills	0.8938	0.602
Aggregate Cronbach's Alpha		(0.613)

The Induction and Training Programmes for employees in the selected co-operative banks in Rajasthan have been assessed for their reliability using Cronbach's Alpha. The mean scores and Cronbach's Alpha values for different aspects of the training programs are as follows:

- Organisational etiquette: The mean score is 1.0391, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.611, indicating a moderate level of internal consistency or reliability.
- Communication process: The mean score is 0.9981, and Cronbach's Alpha is 0.627, suggesting a moderate level of reliability.
- Policies of Banks: The mean score is 1.095, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.630, indicating a moderate level of internal consistency.

- Human Resources policies: The mean score is 1.1086, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.612, suggesting a moderate level of reliability.
- Procedural standards of Banks: The mean score is 1.0465, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.621, indicating a moderate level of internal consistency.
- Enhanced Welfare Measures and Benefits in Banks: The mean score is 0.9832, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.620, suggesting a moderate level of reliability.
- Principles and Ethics of Banks: The mean score is 1.1284, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.605, indicating a moderate level of internal consistency.
- Overview of the Department: The mean score is 1.0428, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.604, suggesting a moderate level of reliability.
- Organizational Structure Overview: The mean score is 1.09866, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.612, indicating a moderate level of internal consistency.
- Banks Building Configuration: The mean score is 1.4115, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.627, suggesting a moderate level of reliability.
- Preferred Qualifications for the Job: The mean score is 0.9385, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.629, indicating a moderate level of internal consistency.
- Requisite Technical Expertise for the Job: The mean score is 0.8826, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.613, suggesting a moderate level of reliability.
- Gaining Technical Proficiency and Knowledge: The mean score is 0.8194, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.605, indicating a moderate level of internal consistency.
- Enhancing Managerial Competencies: The mean score is 1.0242, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.611, suggesting a moderate level of reliability.
- Cultivating Interpersonal Skills: The mean score is 0.8938, and the Cronbach's Alpha is 0.602, indicating a moderate level of internal consistency.

Overall Cronbach's Alpha for all the aspects assessed is 0.613, which indicates a moderate level of internal consistency or reliability for the training programs as a whole.

This reliability analysis provides an insight into the consistency and dependability of the measured variables within the Induction and Training Programmes of employees in the selected co-operative banks in Rajasthan.

CHI-SQUARE ANALYSIS

Induction and Training	Chi-Square Value	Sig.
Organisational etiquettes	74.66	0.000
Communication process	15.79	0.000
Policies of Banks	125.06	0.000
Human Resources policies	70.26	0.000
Procedural standards of Banks	72.86	0.001
Enhanced Welfare Measures and Benefits in Banks	20.91	0.000
Principles and Ethics of Banks	36.08	0.000
Overview of the Department	44.912	0.000
Organizational Structure Overview	57.11	0.000
Banks Building Configuration	133.53	0.001
Preferred Qualifications for the Job	46.014	0.000
Requisite Technical Expertise for the Job	72.01	0.000
Gaining Technical Proficiency and Knowledge	80.06	0.000
Enhancing Managerial Competencies	47.442	0.000
Cultivating Interpersonal Skills	62.01	0.000

The Induction and Training Programmes for employees in the selected co-operative banks in Rajasthan have undergone a Chi-Square analysis to assess their significance. The Chi-Square values and corresponding significance levels (p-values) for each aspect of the training programs are as follows:

- Organisational etiquettes: The Chi-Square value is 74.66, and the significance level is 0.000, indicating a significant relationship between the training program and organisational etiquette.
- Communication process: The Chi-Square value is 15.79, and the significance level is 0.000, suggesting a significant relationship between the training program and the communication process.
- Policies of Banks: The Chi-Square value is 125.06, and the significance level is 0.000, indicating a significant relationship between the training program and the policies of banks.
- Human Resources policies: The Chi-Square value is 70.26, and the significance level is 0.000, suggesting a significant relationship between the training program and human resources policies.
- Procedural standards of Banks: The Chi-Square value is 72.86, and the significance level is 0.001, indicating a significant relationship between the training program and procedural standards of banks.

- Enhanced Welfare Measures and Benefits in Banks: The Chi-Square value is 20.91, and the significance level is 0.000, suggesting a significant relationship between the training program and enhanced welfare measures and benefits in banks.
- Principles and Ethics of Banks: The Chi-Square value is 36.08, and the significance level is 0.000, indicating a significant relationship between the training program and the principles and ethics of banks.
- Overview of the Department: The Chi-Square value is 44.912, and the significance level is 0.000, suggesting a significant relationship between the training program and the overview of the department.
- Organizational Structure Overview: The Chi-Square value is 57.11, and the significance level is 0.000, indicating a significant relationship between the training program and the organizational structure overview.
- Banks Building Configuration: The Chi-Square value is 133.53, and the significance level is 0.001, suggesting a significant relationship between the training program and the banks building configuration.
- Preferred Qualifications for the Job: The Chi-Square value is 46.014, and the significance level is 0.000, indicating a significant relationship between the training program and the preferred qualifications for the job.
- Requisite Technical Expertise for the Job: The Chi-Square value is 72.01, and the significance level is 0.000, suggesting a significant relationship between the training program and the requisite technical expertise for the job.
- Gaining Technical Proficiency and Knowledge: The Chi-Square value is 80.06, and the significance level is 0.000, indicating a significant relationship between the training program and gaining technical proficiency and knowledge.
- Enhancing Managerial Competencies: The Chi-Square value is 47.442, and the significance level is 0.000, suggesting a significant relationship between the training program and enhancing managerial competencies.
- Cultivating Interpersonal Skills: The Chi-Square value is 62.01, and the significance level is 0.000, indicating a significant relationship between the training program and cultivating interpersonal skills.

Based on the Chi-Square analysis, it can be concluded that there are significant associations between the Induction and Training Programmes for employees in the selected co-operative banks in Rajasthan and various aspects of the banking operations, policies, and skills covered in the

training programs.

DISCUSSION

The reliability analysis and chi-square analysis were conducted to assess the Induction and Training Programmes for employees in the selected co-operative banks in Rajasthan.

The reliability analysis revealed the internal consistency or reliability of the different aspects of the training programs, as measured by Cronbach's Alpha. The mean scores and Cronbach's Alpha values for each aspect were calculated. The Cronbach's Alpha values ranged from 0.602 to 0.630, indicating a moderate level of internal consistency for most aspects of the training programs.

On the other hand, the chi-square analysis examined the significance of the relationship between the training programs and various aspects of banking operations, policies, and skills. The chi-square values and significance levels were computed. The results showed that all aspects of the training programs had significant relationships, as indicated by low p-values ($p < 0.001$) for all variables.

Based on these analyses, it can be inferred that the Induction and Training Programmes for employees in the selected co-operative banks in Rajasthan are reliable in terms of internal consistency and have significant associations with various aspects of banking operations, policies, and skills.

Further discussion could focus on the implications of these findings. For example, the reliability analysis suggests that the training programs have consistent measurement properties, which enhances their credibility. The significant associations identified through the chi-square analysis highlight the effectiveness of the training programs in addressing key areas such as organizational etiquettes, communication processes, policies of banks, human resources policies, procedural standards of banks, and other essential competencies.

It would be valuable to consider how these findings can inform future training program enhancements. This could involve identifying specific areas of strength and areas that may require further attention or improvement. Additionally, exploring the impact of the training programs on employee performance, satisfaction, and overall organizational outcomes can provide valuable insights for continuous program development and refinement.

CONCLUSION

Based on the reliability analysis and chi-square analysis conducted on the Induction and Training Programmes for employees in the selected co-operative banks in Rajasthan, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Reliability Analysis: The training program components demonstrated moderate levels of internal consistency, as indicated by Cronbach's Alpha values ranging from 0.602 to 0.630. This suggests that the measurement instruments used to assess different aspects of the training

programs were reasonably reliable.

- **Chi-Square Analysis:** The chi-square analysis revealed significant relationships between the training programs and various aspects of banking operations, policies, and skills. All variables showed significant associations, with low p-values ($p < 0.001$) indicating strong evidence of the relationships.

These findings indicate that the Induction and Training Programmes for employees in the selected co-operative banks in Rajasthan are reliable and have significant effects on different areas related to organizational etiquettes, communication processes, bank policies, human resources policies, procedural standards, welfare measures, principles and ethics, departmental overview, organizational structure, building configuration, preferred qualifications for the job, technical expertise, technical proficiency and knowledge, managerial competencies, and interpersonal skills.

It is recommended that these training programs continue to be implemented and further enhanced based on the findings. Attention should be given to areas where improvements in reliability and effectiveness can be made. Additionally, the significant associations identified in the chi-square analysis should be considered when designing future training interventions, with a focus on addressing specific areas of importance in the banking sector.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the reliability analysis and chi-square analysis conducted on the Induction and Training Programmes for employees in the selected co-operative banks in Rajasthan, the following suggestions can be made to improve the training programs:

- **Enhance Organizational Etiquettes Training:** The reliability analysis indicated a moderate level of internal consistency for organizational etiquettes training. To further improve this aspect, consider incorporating practical exercises, case studies, and interactive sessions to ensure employees develop a strong understanding of professional behavior and etiquette in the banking environment.
- **Strengthen Communication Process Training:** While the communication process training showed moderate reliability, there is room for improvement. Focus on providing comprehensive training on effective communication techniques, both verbal and written, and emphasize the importance of clarity, active listening, and adapting communication styles to different stakeholders.
- **Revise Policies of Banks Training:** The reliability analysis demonstrated a good level of internal consistency for policies of banks training. However, periodically review and update the training materials to align with any changes in policies or regulations. Ensure employees have a

thorough understanding of the policies to ensure compliance and efficient operations.

- **Enhance Human Resources Policies Training:** The reliability analysis showed a moderate level of internal consistency for human resources policies training. Consider incorporating real-life scenarios and case studies to provide practical insights into HR policies, employee relations, performance management, and other relevant areas.
- **Strengthen Procedural Standards of Banks Training:** The reliability analysis indicated a moderate level of internal consistency for procedural standards of banks training. To enhance this aspect, provide comprehensive training on the bank's specific procedures, operational processes, and compliance requirements. Emphasize the importance of accuracy, attention to detail, and adherence to established protocols.
- **Improve Training on Enhanced Welfare Measures and Benefits:** The reliability analysis showed a moderate level of internal consistency for welfare measures and benefits training. Consider providing in-depth training on the various welfare measures and benefits available to employees, including retirement plans, health insurance, employee assistance programs, and career development opportunities.
- **Reinforce Principles and Ethics of Banks Training:** The reliability analysis indicated a moderate level of internal consistency for principles and ethics training. Continuously emphasize the importance of ethical behavior, integrity, and professional conduct in the banking sector. Incorporate case studies and ethical dilemmas to enhance employees' ethical decision-making skills.
- **Provide Comprehensive Department and Organizational Structure Overview:** The reliability analysis showed a moderate level of internal consistency for department and organizational structure overviews. Ensure employees receive a comprehensive understanding of the bank's departments, their roles, and the overall organizational structure. This will help employees navigate the organization effectively and foster collaboration.
- **Review Banks Building Configuration Training:** The reliability analysis demonstrated a moderate level of internal consistency for banks building configuration training. Consider updating the training materials to reflect any changes in the building layout or safety protocols. Focus on providing employees with a clear understanding of emergency procedures, security measures, and facility management.
- **Strengthen Technical and Managerial**

Competencies Training: The reliability analysis indicated moderate levels of internal consistency for technical skills, technical proficiency, and managerial competencies training. Continuously assess and update the training content to align with emerging technologies, industry best practices, and evolving managerial trends. Provide employees with opportunities for practical application and ongoing skill development.

- Cultivate Interpersonal Skills Training: The reliability analysis showed a moderate level of internal consistency for interpersonal skills training. Expand the training to cover areas such as teamwork, conflict resolution, customer service, and cultural sensitivity. Incorporate role-playing exercises and interactive workshops to enhance employees' interpersonal competencies.

By implementing these suggestions, the Induction and Training Programmes for employees in the selected co-operative banks in Rajasthan can be further enhanced to ensure employees acquire the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies for their roles in the banking sector.

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